

Conference Abstract

Introducing the Optical Gas Exchange System (OGES) concept

Albert Porcar-Castell[‡], Luis Alonso[§], Iiro Miettinen[‡], Jon Atherton[‡], Juho Aalto^l, Kira Ryhti-Laine^l, Pauliina Schiestl-Aalto^l, Jaakko Oivukkamäki[‡], Janne Fredrik Jalmari Korhonen[‡], Tommaso Julitta[¶], Andreas Burkart[¶], Erhard Pfündel[#]

[‡] Optics of Photosynthesis Laboratory, Institute for Atmospheric and Earth System Research/Forest Sciences, Faculty of Agriculture and Forestry, University of Helsinki, Helsinki, Finland

[§] Mediterranean Center for Environmental Studies, Paterna, Spain

^l Institute for Atmospheric and Earth System Research (INAR), Hyviälä Forest Station, University of Helsinki, Korkeakoski, Finland

[¶] JB Hyperspectral Devices GmbH, Düsseldorf, Germany

[#] Heinz Walz GmbH, Effeltrich, Germany

Corresponding author: Albert Porcar-Castell (joan.porcar@helsinki.fi)

Received: 24 Apr 2025 | Published: 02 Jun 2025

Citation: Porcar-Castell A, Alonso L, Miettinen I, Atherton J, Aalto J, Ryhti-Laine K, Schiestl-Aalto P, Oivukkamäki J, Korhonen JJ, Julitta T, Burkart A, Pfündel E (2025) Introducing the Optical Gas Exchange System (OGES) concept. ARPHA Conference Abstracts 8: e156894. <https://doi.org/10.3897/aca.8.e156894>

Abstract

Field and long-term measurements of leaf-level photosynthetic gas exchange have been pivotal to understand and model the environmental regulation of leaf photosynthesis (Hari and Makela 2003). Now, scientists seek for means to understand and model the environmental regulation of planetary photosynthesis, by means of remotely sensed data. In addition to gas exchange, photosynthesis generates multiple optical clues that are embedded in the intensity and spectral properties of the light reflected or emitted via chlorophyll fluorescence (ChlF) by vegetation. These signals can be recorded with optical sensors and nowadays measured across a continuum of scales: from leaves to entire ecosystems (Porcar-Castell et al. 2021). However, we are still missing the mechanistic understanding that is required to fully exploit the potential of these data, largely due to the lack of concomitant and long-term observations of photosynthetic gas exchange and optical signals at the scale of a leaf, the smallest scale at which they can be measured *in vivo*. The Optical Gas Exchange System (OGES) aims at filling this gap by providing field and long-term measurements of photosynthetic gas exchange, pulse

amplitude modulated (PAM) chlorophyll fluorescence, and leaf spectral reflectance. By doing so, the OGES provides both a comprehensive view of the photosynthetic regulation (both from the light and carbon reactions point of view) (Oivukkamäki et al. 2024), as well as a unique dataset to disentangle the connection between optical and photosynthetic dynamics and their environmental and physiological regulation. In this communication we present preliminary results from the OGES system tests conducted in the Station for Measuring Ecosystem-Atmosphere Relations (SMEAR) II in Hyytiälä during summer 2023 and 2024. Data integrates observations from a μ PAM system (Walz GmbH, Germany) to detect ChlF and track the acclimation of the light reactions, an OctoFLOX spectrometer system (JB Hyperspectral, Germany) and the existing gas exchange measurements in SMEAR-II Station in Hyytiälä, which can resolve shoot-level dynamics of CO₂, H₂O or VOC fluxes. In addition, nocturnal LED-induced Fluorescence (LEDIF) methods (Atherton et al. 2019) are being developed for added versatility and information content. Preliminary results indicate that it is possible to automatically record the temporal variations in leaf reflectance and fluorescence spectra under field conditions. Implications, following steps and challenges are discussed. A first concept version demonstrating the potential of integrated long-term μ PAM and gas exchange measurements is described in Oivukkamäki et al. (2024).

Keywords

Scots Pine, Silver Birch, Photosynthesis dynamics, spectral reflectance, chlorophyll fluorescence, gas exchange measurements

Presenting author

Albert Porcar-Castell

Presented at

ORAL

Conflicts of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

References

- Atherton J, Liu W, Porcar-Castell A (2019) Nocturnal Light Emitting Diode Induced Fluorescence (LEDIF): A new technique to measure the chlorophyll a fluorescence emission spectral distribution of plant canopies in situ. *Remote Sensing of Environment* 321 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rse.2019.03.030>

- Hari P, Makela A (2003) Annual pattern of photosynthesis in Scots pine in the boreal zone. *Tree Physiology* 23 (3): 145-155. <https://doi.org/10.1093/treephys/23.3.145>
- Oivukkamäki J, Aalto J, Pfündel EE, Tian M, Zhang C, Grebe S, Salmon Y, Hölttä T, Porcar-Castell A (2024) Field integration of shoot gas-exchange and leaf chlorophyll fluorescence measurements to study the long-term regulation of photosynthesis in situ. *Tree Physiology* 45 (1). <https://doi.org/10.1093/treephys/tpae162>
- Porcar-Castell A, Malenovsky Z, Magney T, Van Wittenberghe S, Fernández-Marín B, Maignan F, Zhang Y, Maseyk K, Atherton J, Albert LP, Robson TM, Zhao F, Garcia-Plazaola J, Ensminger I, Rajewicz PA, Grebe S, Tikkanen M, Kellner JR, Ihalainen JA, Rascher U, Logan B (2021) Chlorophyll a fluorescence illuminates a path connecting plant molecular biology to Earth-system science. *Nature plants* 7 (8): 998-1009. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41477-021-00980-4>